

Deliverable D4.1

Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan

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1. Executive Summary

The EOSC-ENTRUST Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan provides guidance, support and resources to maximise the impact of the EOSC-ENTRUST project. This document acts as a reference point for all aspects of EOSC-ENTRUST communications, dissemination and exploitation activities by providing guidelines to project partners internally and harmonising communications and messages to interested external parties.

In this document we present and discuss the following:

- Stakeholders and key messages
- Communications channels
- Branding and communications assets
- Dissemination
- Exploitation
- Communications and dissemination evaluation

The document is live and will be updated continuously as the project progresses.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'.]

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	No
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	Yes
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	No
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No

European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes ¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)	No
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 3 National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes	1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
	2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).	Yes
	3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	Yes
Objective 4 The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and	1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
	2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).	No
	3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).	No

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)	No
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3. Introduction

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability by the joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. Running for three years, the project brings together 34 partners from 15 European countries to develop a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis.

This document outlines the strategy to communicate, disseminate and exploit outputs of the EOSC-ENTRUST project. The strategy aims to capitalise on the collaborative nature of the project by promoting clear, inclusive and targeted communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts.

This deliverable is part of the EOSC-ENTRUST Communication and Outreach Work Package (WP4/5/6). The Work Package aims to develop and implement the project-wide communications and outreach strategy, ensuring key stakeholders including scientists, industry, policymakers and the public have awareness of the project and opportunities to engage, use project outputs and provide feedback to partners.

In order to develop this document we draw upon:

- the experience and skills of the [ELIXIR External Relations team](#)
- lessons learned from the delivery of the Communication Work Packages across multiple [EU projects](#)
- the specific project needs defined by the interaction with different Work Packages, the coordination team and project partners
- the policy advice and public engagement expertise of [HDR UK](#), UK's national institute for health data science

4. Description of work

4.1 Stakeholders and key messages

4.1.1 Stakeholders

The main EOSC-ENTRUST stakeholders are:

- Data users from academia and industry
- Resource providers from academia and industry, including public service providers, data owners and controllers, research infrastructures and Trusted Research Environment providers
- European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and European Health Data Space (EHDS) ecosystems
- National funders and policymakers
- National and global standardisation bodies, such as GA4GH

4.1.2 Key messages

The EOSC-ENTRUST key messages are:

- **Objectives:**
EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis.
- **Motivation:**
The fragmented landscape of secure environments in different national centres, organisations and research communities poses challenges for both users and providers. Researchers are faced with many different systems and access procedures; providers need to manage federated access across multiple, potentially incompatible, technology and governance frameworks.
- **Solution:**
EOSC-ENTRUST has identified four driver projects covering genomics, clinical trials, social science and public-private partnerships to benchmark capabilities, inform blueprint design and demonstrate secure data analysis using federated workflows.
- **Outcomes:**
Enabling an operational, open and FAIR EOSC ecosystem:
 - Expand EOSC's access to resources and ensure the opening of valuable data sets for novel research through a standard set of methods able to effectively enable sensitive data sharing, processing and analysis.
 - Demonstrate that FAIR data workflows with sensitive data are securely managed and can benefit both the data providers and the science community.

- Facilitate new ways of using sensitive data sets with the emergence of TREs.

4.1.3 Communication goal

The main purpose of the EOSC-ENTRUST communication activities is to build trust and awareness with project stakeholders. The project aims to inform, build trust and reach out to society to show how the EOSC-ENTRUST project contributes to tackling research challenges. The communication activities cover the project's results and outcomes and the target audience from the project consortium to key stakeholders, such as data users, data providers, funders and standardisation bodies.

Communicating the impact of the EOSC-ENTRUST project is one of the key communication goals. The following are impact categories indicated on the ELIXIR website, which are also relevant to the EOSC-ENTRUST project and can be applied to ensure the impact of EOSC-ENTRUST communication activities².

- **Benefits of working together (relationship capital):** facilitate knowledge-sharing and cooperation.
- **Data management resource uptake:** work to increase their usage and appreciation by users.
- **Equal opportunity:** raise awareness of diversity and inclusiveness.
- **Policy influence:** ensure that policy-makers are aware of the benefits of open and FAIR science and Trusted Research Environments.
- **Public awareness:** raise the public's awareness of open science and the need for Trusted Research Environments, including their socio-economic benefits.
- **Research dissemination:** ensure increased awareness of developments related to research infrastructure and their resources.
- **Research efficiency:** make infrastructure, resources and processes faster, easier to use, and more integrated.
- **Research infrastructure sustainability:** work to increase its visibility and appreciation by funders.
- **Skills development (human capital):** foster better skills for users and service providers.

4.2 Communications channels

4.2.1 Website

The primary communications channel for the EOSC-ENTRUST project is the main website: <https://eosc-entrust.eu/>. The website provides comprehensive information about the project and will be the source for future updates and events. The primary goals of the project website are:

² <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/more-examples>

- To communicate the EOSC-ENTRUST project, its objectives and its organisation clearly.
- To promote activities and achievements of the project, for example, events and news stories of the project's progress.
- To advertise the impact of the EOSC-ENTRUST project to key stakeholders, policy-makers, funders and experts who work with data management and data analysis.

4.2.1.1 Website content

The ELIXIR Hub External Relations team is part of the EOSC-ENTRUST Communication and Outreach Work Package (WP4/5/6) and has full editorial control over the website content. However, in developing new content, ELIXIR Hub will regularly consult project partners and other relevant groups within the project as well as external stakeholders. All materials to be published on the website should be sent to webmaster@elixir-europe.org.

4.2.1.2 Spelling conventions

The following conventions should be applied to the EOSC-ENTRUST website as well as to other communication outputs.

- EOSC-ENTRUST, always capitalised with a hyphen between EOSC and ENTRUST
- Use English [EC style guide](#)³

4.2.2 EOSC-ENTRUST newsletter

The EOSC-ENTRUST newsletter for external stakeholders will be released quarterly. The newsletter will present news and updates on the project as well as activities and achievements. All content published in the newsletter must be directly related to EOSC-ENTRUST, some announcements from third parties will be considered if relevant to the mission or the activities of the project.

The newsletter subscription form is embedded in the website and back-issues of the newsletter will be available to view. The newsletter will be promoted via the EOSC-ENTRUST website and social media and the newsletter will be managed and created via the email marketing platform MailerLite.

While the ELIXIR Hub is responsible for creating and managing the newsletter and the mailing list, the content for the newsletter is developed in consultation with Work Package Leaders. In this context, ELIXIR Hub offers:

- A [registration form](#) for all partners, external stakeholders and interested parties to subscribe to the newsletter.

3

https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/c45f5b70-2d0e-4da7-b181-b5fe3a16c4bb_en

- Extensive communications coverage to gather new subscribers on social media, mailing lists, [ELIXIR's website](#) and the [EOSC-ENTRUST website](#).
- A newsletter archive via the [website](#).
- Create a planning sheet and editorial calendar to programme the newsletter after a key date for the project.

4.2.2.1 Target audience

The newsletter is open to subscription from any individual and the project is focused on a broad demographic of scientists (e.g. biologists, data scientists and social scientists) and policymakers. Therefore the content will be understandable and accessible with information provided to link to further technical details.

4.2.2.2 Newsletter template

A template for the EOSC-ENTRUST newsletter has been created and will be used for the planning of project newsletters. Contents listed in the template include (but are not limited to) project highlights, project news, project deliverables and milestones, recommended events and recommended reads.

4.2.3 Social media

In addition to promoting specific activities of EOSC-ENTRUST and driving more visitors to the website, the project's social media strategy focuses on community building and networking. The Twitter/X ([@eosc_entrust](#)) and LinkedIn ([EOSC-ENTRUST](#)) accounts have been set up and are managed by ELIXIR Communications Officers within the External Relations team.

4.2.3.1 Hashtags

The project has close relations with European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), therefore, the hashtag [#EOSC](#) should be used in related posts. The hashtag will bring up existing tweets from other EOSC-related projects.

Other hashtags that can be used in posts are keywords related to EOSC-ENTRUST's key objectives, for example, [#openscience](#), [#opendata](#) and [#TrustedResearchEnvironments](#). Hashtags related to the project's outcomes or events can be created in the future when needed.

4.2.3.2 Tagging

Whenever possible and relevant, social media posts should tag partners and/or project groups whose work is being communicated. To ease the process of identifying the accounts for all project partners, a publicly available [Twitter/X list](#) of EOSC-ENTRUST project partners' official Twitter/X accounts has been created. As a project funded under the

European Union's Horizon Europe Programme, [@HorizonEU](#) will be used in posts when mentioning the outputs of the project.

4.3 Branding

The EOSC-ENTRUST logo and branding guidelines are available on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive to facilitate correct usage of the branding from project partners.

4.3.1 Logo

The logo is co-branded with EOSC, reflecting the strong links between EOSC-ENTRUST and EOSC. The logo was designed in collaboration with EOSC.

4.3.2 Branding guidelines

To facilitate the ease of use of communication materials designed for EOSC-ENTRUST, the [EOSC-ENTRUST branding guidelines](#) are presented in a presentation (PowerPoint) format and are available on the project Google Drive. This enables project partners who wish to present the EOSC-ENTRUST project to easily lift logo, design and funding acknowledgements from the guidelines for use in their own presentations.

Project partners are also welcome to reach out to the Communications Officer at the ELIXIR Hub should they require further visual materials or assistance in developing presentations for EOSC-ENTRUST.

All existing communications materials are accessible on the [EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive](#) for project partners to access and use.

4.3.3 Templates

ELIXIR Hub provides templates for a range of communication activities and reports following the branding guidelines.

All EOSC-ENTRUST presentations should use the official template. The templates include:

- Presentation slides
- Documents
- Deliverables and milestones
- Posters

[Link to EOSC-ENTRUST Templates](#) (requires access to project Google Drive)

4.4 Communications assets

4.4.1 Graphics, icons and stock images

As detailed in Section 4.3 the EOSC-ENTRUST logo and branding guidelines are available on the project Google Drive to facilitate the correct usage of the EOSC-ENTRUST branding.

Requests for further materials and details on their usage can be directed to info@elixir-europe.org.

4.4.2 Boilerplate text

The boilerplate text can be reused in new contexts or applications without any significant changes. Examples of use include websites of the project partners, news and press releases and publications.

Boilerplate text

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments for sensitive data and drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. It brings together providers of operational TREs from 15 European countries to implement, validate and promote their capabilities using shared standards and common legal, operational and technical language.

4.5 Dissemination

Dissemination is the process of ensuring all scientific outputs are openly available and in forms that are easily accessible, understandable and reusable. Dissemination fosters the use and uptake of results and outcomes. In contrast, communications covers the sharing and promotion of wider project efforts. Dissemination activities target audiences that are likely to use the results in their own work, for instance, peers and experts in and outside of the project, including policy-makers. Communications activities target multiple audiences beyond the project consortium, including the media and the public.

4.5.1 External events

To raise awareness about the main aim and outputs of the EOSC-ENTRUST project, project partners are encouraged to attend key events organised by external parties or organisations. By presenting at external events, the relevant scientific communities will be able to use the results and outcomes of the project in their work. Some possible events could include (but are not limited to) the following: conferences, workshops, EOSC symposium, Horizon Europe and other EU-funded projects' events, such as EOSC-SIESTA and EOSC-TITAN's events.

Name of event/conference	Organiser	Frequency	Focus
EOSC Symposium	EOSC	Annual	EOSC ecosystem
ELIXIR All Hands Meeting	ELIXIR	Annual	Bioinformatics, Research data management
European Conference on Computational Biology (ECCB)	University of Turku and CSC – IT Center for Science (2024 edition)	Biennial	Data and algorithms for health and science (for 2024 edition)
BioHackathon Europe	ELIXIR	Annual	Bioinformatics services, resources and training
UK Trusted Research Environment (TRE) Annual Community Meeting	UK TRE	Annual	TREs
GA4GH plenary	GA4GH	Annual	Standards and policy frameworks for genomic and health data sharing

4.5.2 Publications

Publication is one of the key dissemination activities as it can help increase awareness and publicity of technical knowledge resulting from project implementation. Project partners are encouraged to add manuscripts, preprints and peer-reviewed publications to the [EOSC-ENTRUST Quarterly Status Report document](#).

EOSC-ENTRUST acknowledgement for communications activities:

“EOSC-ENTRUST project receives funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101131056”

4.5.3 Zenodo

A [Zenodo community](#) has been created and is used as a home for project outputs, such as deliverables, posters, presentation slides, training materials and other project-related documents. Efforts will be made to ensure outputs are published promptly for good visibility and impact.

Dissemination will be facilitated by the use of appropriate metadata when uploading to Zenodo (e.g. grant agreement number 101131056, Horizon Europe and ORCID IDs of the co-authors), which will improve FAIR metadata for discoverability, as well as project-wide aggregation by EC’s OpenAIRE. The combined number of views and downloads of the documents will be used to evaluate project progress.

4.5.4 Tracking and monitoring

Dissemination efforts are the responsibility of all work packages, in contrast to communications efforts which fall primarily under WP4/5/6. All dissemination activities contributed by EOSC-ENTRUST partners will be added to the “Dissemination activities” tab in the [EOSC-ENTRUST Reporting Tracker](#) by project partners.

4.5.5 Alignment with SIESTA and TITAN

EOSC-ENTRUST’s sister projects, EOSC-SIESTA and EOSC-TITAN, were funded in the same call to provide trusted environments for sensitive data management in EOSC. The EOSC-ENTRUST Communication and Outreach Work Package (WP4/5/6) will align with EOSC-SIESTA and EOSC-TITAN through communications activities, including regular contact between communications officers through emails and meetings, amplifying projects’ activities on social media, mutual invitations to events and sister projects’ updates in newsletters.

4.6 Exploitation

Exploitation activities enable the concrete use of research results, either directly by project participants or indirectly by others outside of the project, including industry. Exploitation of results can be done through scientific, economic, political, or societal exploitation routes, turning results into value for society. Where dissemination describes and makes results visible to audiences that may use the results, exploitation is the actual use of the results, during and after the project.

As with communications and dissemination efforts, exploitation efforts are tracked in the [EOSC-ENTRUST Quarterly Status Report document](#) and regularly analysed, reviewed and reported. Examples of exploitation efforts include informing suggestions through policy briefs as well as industry engagement through events and newsletters.

4.6.1 Policy briefs

In collaboration with other Work Packages, EOSC-ENTRUST WP4/5/6 will create three policy briefs during the project period. The policy briefs will consolidate insights from the technical alignment workshops, main outputs from the drivers and key recommendations from other Work Packages.

The policy brief aims to inform national policies for the implementation of secure and trusted research environment infrastructure, including governance, data access processes, data use transparency and legal requirements for TREs.

The three policy briefs will focus on different phases of the project, from mobilisation and early adoption to maximising impact:

- The first policy brief will summarise early emerging recommendations informed by each Work Package.
- The second policy brief will provide policy recommendations for relevant stakeholders to enable implementation of the infrastructure requirements.
- The third policy brief will summarise insights, challenges and opportunities highlighted through each driver project work.

The policy briefs will be disseminated on the EOSC-ENTRUST project website, Zenodo, social media as well as newsletters.

4.7 Evaluation

The evaluation of EOSC-ENTRUST communications will be carried out continuously. It will summarise and analyse the impact of each communication channel and adjust the strategy or individual communication actions if necessary. Reports on EOSC-ENTRUST communications activities and their evaluation will be shared with the project consortium regularly through WP4/5/6 meetings, Work Package Leaders meetings and other presentations as required.

4.7.1 Communications metrics

The communication metrics will measure the engagement rate, the quality of communications and the reach outside the EOSC-ENTRUST project. Data collected will include:

- Web traffic metrics

- Performance of EOSC-ENTRUST newsletter provided by MailerLite
 - Number of subscribers
 - Click rate
 - Opening rate
 - Benchmark with other comparable newsletters
- Zenodo analytics
 - Views
 - Downloads
- Twitter/X analytics
 - Followers
 - Number of posts
 - Number of posts' like and share
- LinkedIn analytics
 - Followers
 - Number of posts
 - Post impression and engagement rate

4.7.2 Dissemination progress

To monitor dissemination progress, [EOSC-ENTRUST Quarterly Status Report document](#) has been created for partners to input information on external activities, including events that partners have attended or presented at, as well as publications submitted during the project period.

4.7.3 Exploitation efforts

The outcomes of project exploitation can be difficult to evaluate since they include the actual use of results after the project as well as during it. However, the exploitation efforts could be evaluated by analysing metrics including the numbers of views and downloads of policy briefs, web visits, the audiences (size and type) of industry and stakeholder events and newsletters. The exploitation efforts are also documented in the [EOSC-ENTRUST Quarterly Status Report document](#).

5. Conclusion

The Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan defines the communication channels, the EOSC-ENTRUST branding, the communication assets, the evaluation criteria and the communication guidance that provide the means for effective internal and external communication. The evaluation criteria will be used to monitor the effectiveness of the communication strategy providing the means to act and ensure that the communication strategy remains fit for purpose throughout the project lifetime.

At the moment of writing this communication strategy (M06 of the EOSC-ENTRUST project), communication channels and branding are already in place and being used across all Work Packages, such as Work Package meetings and the EOSC-ENTRUST kick-off meeting. In the coming months, we will evaluate the effectiveness of the communication channels, and use this information to improve the current strategy.